

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See *informed consent sheet*

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized transcript of the recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	16/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	MÓNICA DOMÍNGUEZ MARTÍN
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	MARGARITA RUIZ PAVÓN
Affiliation of the expert	Council of Fuensalida (Toledo), 12.000 inhabitants
Position/Job description	Management Expert of the Legal Branch/Secretary
Gender	FEMALE
Years of experience	More than 20 years
Area of expertise	civil servant, legal expert
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL/URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	In your opinion, what is the impact that increasing population movements from the countryside to cities have on local governments?
	It translates into depopulation and population decline: impact on local skills, reduction of skills.
1.1	<p><i>Do you know any public policies or best practices regarding the changing urban-rural relationships? Please consider practices in the following five areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Local responsibilities and public services.</i> - <i>Local financial arrangements.</i> - <i>Structure of local government.</i> - Intergovernmental relations of local governments. - People's participation in local decision-making.
2	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?
	In the municipality of Fuensalida there is no depopulation problem. Lately, the City Council has grown. It is located 28 Km. from the provincial capital (Toledo) and a shoe factory is located in the municipality, which employs workers. Therefore, it attracts a population, especially the immigrant population.
3.	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?

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	Both elements are important. At same level.
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Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

GENERAL QUESTIONS ABOUT THE PROVINCES IN TERMS OF THE PROVISION OF SERVICES

4.	Indicate some factors of success/ failure of the role of the provinces in the Spanish local structure.
	Success: agility and facilitating certain administrative procedures. They play a fundamental role in small municipalities, but in medium and large municipalities their role is not relevant. Failure: sometimes the procedures managed from the province (aid, subsidies) are too bureaucratic, too procedural.
5.	To what extent does the province increase or decrease the centralization of power?
	The province plays little role in Fuensalida because it is a rich municipality, with a lot of income. That is why it is less dependent on the provincial (from an economic point of view) and, for the same reason, they do not notice the centralization of power. They are very autonomous.
6.	Do the provinces compete (or even threaten) the legitimacy or autonomy of the municipalities?
	Absolutely. The County Council helps financially or functionally (but nothing else). It is a plus.
7.	What impact the provinces have on the execution of powers by municipalities, especially those with a population of fewer than 20,000 inhabitants (rural areas)?
	No. For the same reasons.

PROVINCIAL SERVICES

8	Does the Provincial Government provide any service in the municipality? Which one?
	No. There is an agreement with the Autonomous Tax Management Agency. There is also an agreement with the fire extinguishing consortium.

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9	<i>If the previous answer is affirmative, how do you assess the importance of this service for the municipality?</i>
	No. It is not one of the main services. It is helpful, but a very important volume is self-managed.
10	<i>Do you think that the City Council could manage these services if it had better financing?</i>
	Yes. It is not a question of funding. It is a small part.

TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

11	<i>Does your City Council receive technical assistance from the Provincial Government? And from the Autonomous Community?</i>
	Not in this municipality. They are self-sufficient and have their own technical staff (sports management technician, architect, local employment agent...).
12	<i>Does the Provincial Government collaborate in municipal procedures?</i>
	No.
13	<i>Do you consider that such assistance is adequate?</i>
	No.
14	<i>What is the procedure through which the City Council requests and obtains this assistance?</i>
	In grant management material. The bases of the call are approved by the Provincial Council (which also resolves the procedure) and the processing is by the City Council.

DEMOGRAPHY AND POPULATION MOVEMENTS

15	<i>Do you consider that the role of the province in the provision of services influences the migratory flow to large cities?</i> 15.1 In what way? 15.2 Could you offer an example?
	It is not a problem for this municipality. It does not notice it.
16	<i>Does the aging of the population affect the provision of services and the role that carries the province?</i> 16.1 To what extent?
	It does affect, although they have less perception of this problem, because the problem of population aging does not affect them as much. They have a large young population. For this

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	reason, social services are focused on the care and protection of the elderly, but there are also policies and services aimed at the young population.
17	What other demographic changes affect service delivery?
	There is a large young population, in addition to the arrival of immigrants. The City Council has a day center for the elderly. They also have services for the unemployed. There has been a center for women, although not currently (but there is an agreement with the Provincial Council for this support services for women).
18	In your opinion, does the municipality have a dispersed population?
	It does not know it.
19	If so, to what extent does dispersion affect services provision and the role of the province?
	Does not affect this municipality.
20	To attract or retain the population to rural municipalities, what structure of municipal services do you consider would be more favorable?
	It is not a problem in this municipality.
21	Do you consider that the role of the province in the provision of services influences the migratory flow to larger cities? 21.1 How or in which way? 21.2 Could you offer an example?
	More than the provincial influence the provision of services (more and better). It believes that it is not necessary to undertake reforms or use other structures. They do well with the current setup.

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